

INTERNATIONAL MONETARY POLICY, THE FLAWS IN THE PAST, PRESENT, AND FUTURE SYSTEMS

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Abstract

ECENT proposals for international monetary reform, with much of the discussion centered on these, reveal a confusion of purpose and a lack of a coherent principle that is only likely to result in disappointment or disaster. This is because it is only likely that the current system will continue to function as it does. We will not know how to do it unless we have a clear idea of what it is that we want, yet the difficulties are not precisely defined, the objectives that are expected are not compatible with each other, and the techniques that are supposed to be used to achieve them frequently contradict each other. This article aims to clarify the situation by outlining the possible targets of international monetary policy, the flaws in the past, present, and future systems that have been proposed so far, and an alternative plan that has the promise of a real realization of the results we will achieve. [C The two main goals of freedom and stability are of the utmost significance and are sufficiently all-encompassing to include all other, more specific goals. When seen at first sight, it may seem as if freedom and stability are destined to be at odds with one another.

Keywords: *International Monetary Policy, Present and Future Systems of Money, International Monetary, Monetary Policy*

1. Introduction

This is because freedom implies harmony, harmony, and harmony in a dynamic environment, with mobility rather than stability or status serving as its focal point. Although trade and

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movement are indispensable components of both liberty and development, the practice of such exchange has no redeeming qualities because it contributes nothing to the achievement of these goals, results in displacement that is invariably negative, and can only be unjust if it serves the interests of a specific group. Therefore, the goal should be to produce stability that helps to liberal growth and that can be protected without deviating from the possibility for movement, which is vital to freedom. This should be the focus of the work that has to be done. The construction of stable price levels in any or all nations may be an avenue toward the promotion of freedom; yet freedom cannot coexist with the preservation of constant links between the prices of different goods. If the nations concerned are willing to implement the same monetary policies (regardless of whether they aim at stable price levels or not), then having fixed exchange rates between currencies is a workable policy; but, if this is not the case, then this policy will be disruptive.

As a result, when it comes to international relations, we need to try to strike a balance between the freedom of the individual, the sovereignty of the nations, and the welfare of the international community. The existing, semi-official plans for worldwide monetary regulation have several shortcomings, the most significant of which is that they will not be successful unless significant constraints are placed on the freedom of people and the autonomy of nations. The writers of this work are unwilling to make the required deductions from their recommendations; as a result, their plans are inconsistent and unproductive, rather than immediately authoritative. On the other hand, the restrictions on liberty that they foresee are avoidable, not only without causing any harm to the international order that they profess to uphold, but also with the potential to bring about significant improvements to that system. To provide evidence in support of this assertion, we will now proceed to examine, in the following section, the fundamentals of international monetary relations, the history of attempts to resolve these relations in a manner that is satisfactory, and the reforms that are suggested by the inadequacies of these attempts.

It is possible to believe that free exchange rates will be the agenda of liberals rather than those who prioritize stability, while fixed exchange rates will be the program of those who prefer to place an emphasis on stability at the price of freedom. Professor Viner, who was not present at either camp, suggests that it is possible to speculate that they just know what it is that they do not want. However, the situation is not as straightforward as it may seem. Intelligent proponents

of fixed exchange rates will not prevent adjustments, but they will do so in an automatically established harmony, to a considerable part, in the direction of such movements in the national price levels of the different nations involved. This will not prevent adjustments. Intelligent Supporters of Unregulated Currency Exchange Rates Intelligent proponents of free exchange rates, on the other hand, must necessarily turn their backs on many people who believe that stability is important. However, the stability that is important is not the illusory stability of a frozen exchange rate structure; rather, it is the relationship between the (independently determined) domestic purchasing forces of various currencies and the foreign purchasing forces of those currencies. claims to have stable conditions. exchange) The majority of those who advocate for free exchange rates base their beliefs on the consistency of the price level in their own nation as opposed to the consistency of exchange rates with nations that have price levels that are prone to fluctuation. It is conceivable to obtain some (inadequate) synthesis of freedom and stability when exchange rates are either set or entirely free. However, if Professor Viner is correct, most individuals do not want to make a definitive decision amongst the available options. However, since such development is not now available, the widespread desire for a hybrid system is comprehensible, even if it is not logical.

2. Currency Exchange Rate

The reality is that we cannot choose a system for the currency exchange rate in a vacuum. If fixed exchange rates are an unavoidable necessity, then we should work toward achieving stability in the relationship between different national price levels. This is because the relationship between different national price levels is, in and of itself, a potentially dangerous anomaly when there are no fixed exchange rates. On the other hand, if we do not want or are unable to get a monetary policy identity in all nations that would lead to stability in the connection between national price levels, then it is essential that exchange rates be allowed to float to maintain freedom and stability. The only issue that can be asked in this scenario is whether or whether it is preferable for people to follow what they believe to be their own interests, or spend money, given that exchange rates are exclusively decided by free commerce. Therefore, a slightly chaotic exchange rate may be looked on as a sequential preference in comparison to the freedom of mobility. This is not precisely the same thing as a hybrid system.

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This "regular" movement, on the other hand, can be achieved either by preventing excessive, or non-functional, variations in a structure that is in constant flow, or by maintaining a constant ratio between them for an extended period. Both strategies are effective in achieving the desired result. Both approaches have been used in the past, and we will return to them later as part of our examination of the historical circumstances.

Both hypotheses start from the premise that it is impossible to anticipate that all nations would agree to use the same monetary policy and keep it in place; both also assume that no one can stop them from buying and selling foreign currency whenever and wherever they wish. "Control" is the name of a business that competes in the market as one of the parties. In contrast, the term "control" has a monopoly status inside the German system. It decides who is allowed to possess the money and forces everyone who does own it to submit to the "control" on conditions that will be enforced anyway. In a society dominated by nationalist ideologies, it is impossible to devise an automated system that can adjust currency exchange rates to independently decided price levels.

None of these presumptions is necessarily true; nevertheless, if they were, it would be possible to make a case for sound exchange rate management of some sort or another, which would be plausible at the very least and potentially indisputable as well. Because of the potential significance of fixed exchange rates, every effort should be taken to preserve the crucial fixity in national price-level relations that is required to keep them in place under any political system that asserts a commitment to freedom.

3. Long-Standing Cultural Preference for Using Predetermined Odds

There is a long-standing cultural preference for using predetermined odds. It is true that fluctuations in the stock market do not always need to have substantial harmful impacts on their own if they are constantly in close accord with changes in the linkages between national price levels (many of which are volatile). Even in the country with a fixed price level, the relationships between the prices of individual commodities will, of course, not remain constant. However, this is not something that should be desired, and in the case of the exchange rate, nothing will happen to significantly distort the price structure. This will be the case with

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economies that are geographically separated. However, it is difficult even to broach the subject of guaranteeing beneficial movements of exchange rates between different independent currencies under any of the monetary systems that we now have. Although hedging may minimize risk in short-term contracts involving foreign currency, it is also possible for it to be stated in long-term contracts. If it were more important for a country to have stable exchange relations with such a currency than to pursue an independent monetary policy, it would be simple to bind the currency to the currency of the stable currency country and thus secure the fixity in the exchange rate structure. This would be the case if it were more important for the country to have stable exchange relations with such a currency than to pursue an independent monetary policy. On the other hand, it is more difficult to secure and enforce worldwide agreement on the "right" rate at any one moment. This is because the "proper" rate is always changing. In addition, individuals in business would rather have fluctuating pricing levels than unstable exchange rates (probably because they are more conscious of the instability of exchange rates rather than the less volatile, but indeed far more important, movements in price levels). Fixed exchange rates, even when attained in a group of national price levels that are just moving in concord rather than being stable, tend to favor desired international transactions.

This is because fixed exchange rates are more predictable. If the purchasing power of the currencies that are used to express international obligations could reach a level of stability that has not yet been accomplished, this would, of course, be of much greater benefit to the parties to the contracts as well as to the countries that are borrowing and lending money than simply pegging their currencies. The collapse of the international credit structure in the early 1930s, which was attributable to the general downward movement of price levels under the regime of fixed exchange rates, was far more devastating than anywhere that fluctuating exchange rates could be held. This was the case because of the general downward movement of price levels. has been found to be at fault. On the other hand, this merely serves to demonstrate that stable exchange rates are not compatible with ever-evolving national monetary policies and that a fixed price level should be favored instead. It is true that the fixity of exchange rates would have minimal effect if foreign investment had always been in the form of stocks. However, this is not the case.

However, when these investments take the form of fixed monetary obligations in certain national currencies, the real amount of the principal and interest payments are often provided to the interested parties in their own currencies. This is because each country has its own currency. The desire for a fixed exchange rate, which reflects the pursuit of some degree of stability in an uncertain world, frequently fosters insecurity that is readily expected to diminish but can still be a crucial factor in ensuring that overall prices remain stable. This is because the craving for a fixed exchange rate reflects the pursuit of some degree of stability in an uncertain world. Despite this, the British Stock Clearing Account was able to operate this system with some degree of success two or three years prior to 1936, which was the year when the Tripartite Agreement on "stability" was achieved. However, it is possible that this occurred simply because the United States did not take any preventative action in response to its offer to freely buy gold at a predetermined price.

There are four conceivable piles of national monetary systems, but only one of them (which we have never had) can deliver a level of stability that we can genuinely want. These four piles of national monetary systems are as follows: There is an appropriate structure for the exchange rate that corresponds to each, two of which are fixed and two of which are floating. Adoption of one of the four is unavoidable, and if freedom is assumed, the correct exchange rate structure will be automatically decided. In terms of the phenomena of price levels, the following illustration of the four potential groupings of systems is conceivable when the relevant exchange rate structure is considered:

On the other hand, if none of these monetary policies is acceptable or can be implemented, then a flexible exchange rate system is something that can be done as an alternative to strict regulations or complete anarchy. Under these circumstances, any attempt to establish the fixity of rates would accumulate disequilibrium, providing speculators with a multitude of artificially held weak currencies beyond their natural value, and supporting what is a precarious international monetary structure for the time being. National pricing levels have the potential to vary from any degree of integration if such flexibility is not permitted in the market. Nostalgia for a stable exchange rate is irrelevant under these conditions since there is no way to approach it with any degree of certainty. This was the case at a time when different countries throughout the globe used a variety of different monetary standards and there was no involvement by

governments in the currency exchange markets. Even while some nations used gold as their standard of value, others used silver, and none of them used a bimetallic standard that was successful, neither the absolute national price levels nor the connection between gold-based and silver-based currencies were stable. Naturally, the rates of exchange between them did not remain constant throughout time. The same thing happened before when certain nations used one or another metallic currency as their monetary standard, while others relied on a paper standard that was not freely convertible.

4. Equivalent Of Fixed Exchange Rates

This was prevalent throughout the years 1919–1925, and to a lesser degree, it continued into the post–1931 era. During that historical period, naturally, the price levels of countries with various standards were established very independently of one another, and exchange rates fluctuated (abnormally). Although the equivalent of fixed exchange rates is a significant constancy in the relationship between price levels in the few countries involved, within this scheme there must be a certain "game" to quickly eliminate the imbalances that always arise in international trade and finance. These imbalances can be caused by several factors, including but not limited to differences in national production costs, differences in labor costs, and differences in commodity prices. This "game" is only possible when there are (even tiny) deviations from a perfect constancy in the connection between price levels. This is because exchange rates cannot be changed when they are totally set. However, this process may be helped along by forward movements of currency rates that are kept within a small range. This is done so that the underlying stable nature of the exchange rates is not compromised. (The technique that incorporates both adjustments will be regarded as the gold standard on a global scale.) Rates of Exchange That Can Change In turn, currency movements should not simply reflect the variations that occur in the link between the price levels of the different nations that are involved when floating exchange rates are in place. This is because floating exchange rates allow for more exchange rate flexibility. This will mean that equilibrium will be restored in some cases with slightly less than strict proportionality to the deviation in the relative domestic purchasing power of the corresponding currencies, and in other cases with a slightly greater movement in exchange rates.

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In some cases, this will mean that equilibrium will be restored with slightly less than strict proportionality to the deviation in the relative domestic purchasing power of the corresponding currencies. Nevertheless, the "game" is orders of magnitude less than the sympathetic, simultaneous, commonplace, and proportionate fluctuations that take place at unstable price levels that are connected to each other by fixed exchange rates. This is the case regardless of whatever technique of adjustment is used. "Game" should be included in every system, but its significance lies in its qualitative rather than quantitative aspects. The system was prevalent during much of the nineteenth century and throughout the early part of the twentieth century, right up to the onset of the First World War.

Price levels are fixed in certain nations, but their links to the price levels in other countries, particularly those countries in which there is no such thing as price stability, are always subject to change, and exchange rates are allowed to fluctuate freely. Although the British did not have the resources to "manage" exchange rates, some convergence was achieved when an attempt was made to stabilize the price level in the British Isles shortly after Great Britain abandoned gold in 1931. This occurred shortly after the Great Depression, which began in 1929. The British Currency Balancing Account was able to change the (up until that point, wild) movements of exchange rates in either direction to put them on a fully functional footing in later years, when an attempt was made to improve this system. In those years, the British Currency Balancing Account was successful.

Long-Term Equilibrium in International Calculations

Although none of these systems was incompatible with freedom or a long-term equilibrium in international calculations, none of them were particularly good at either preserving stability or swiftly resolving short-term disruptions. In addition, each one of them was subject to increasing intervention by government officials who were equally opposed to the concept of a comprehensive laissez faire about price levels as well as exchange rates, the price level movements that accompanied the system of fixed exchange rates. As a result of this intervention, the international gold standard failed, and in many countries, the international gold standard was not replaced by a free or even functionally controlled system of exchange rates;

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rather, the establishment of this system was what took its place. In the case of various metallic units, this circumstance has been altered. The issue of whether the price on commodity markets affects the exchange rate between metal currencies, or vice versa, or, more likely, if there is a connection between the two, remains unanswered. It is more probable that there is interaction between the two. Arbitrage has always been the connection between the price of commodities and the price of stocks, but there is no way to draw any conclusions about the chain of causation between the two. When it was first established in 1932, the British Exchange Equalization Account could only make use of pound in terms of its resources. Since it did not own gold or any other currency, it was unable to prevent a decline in the value of the pound's exchange rate; however, it was able to prevent a rise in the value of the pound's exchange rate. After then, the account began to accumulate resources in the form of gold and several other forms of foreign cash. These rates were frequently inconsistent with the relative domestic purchasing power of the currencies involved and could only be exercised through a complete government monopoly on international transactions. A prime example of this type of government monopoly was Germany, which was a major economic power. A monopoly of this kind would very certainly stifle competition and cause distortions in international commerce. The choice between potent weapon methods covers the entire field of trade and finance, so that there are no useful ends. This is because under the monopoly of foreign transactions that was initiated due to the prevention of the automatic elimination of temporary disturbances in the field of international trade and finance, the transformation of temporary imbalances into permanent imbalances and the collapse of the existing exchange rate structure, the choice between potent weapon methods was initiated.

Despite this, new semi-official suggestions for worldwide monetary reform would create a system of fixed rates that will be maintained until the time of collapse. However, there is no provision for the adoption of a globally unified price level policy in these ideas. System of the International Monetary Fund, Type Four Fixed exchange rates are the fourth type of international monetary system that is compatible with freedom. However, this type of system has not yet been implemented in all countries with price levels that have remained constant. On the other hand, this could be what we want to accomplish with our work. In a contemporary economy, there is an undeniable and pressing need to maintain price stability. Dr. It is not

required for the first line of White's proposal for the United Nations and the United Nations

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Stabilization Fund (New York Times, April 7, 1943, page 17) to have the main goal of stabilizing foreign nations. The United States and the nations that relate to it each have their own exchange rates. "Stability" is not specifically defined, but while establishing the plan, it is evident that a desire for constant rates is there. Despite this, there are instances in which it is unwillingly permitted to modify rates, which is essential. In his article titled "International Clearing Union, British Information Services, New York, New York, 1943," Lord Keynes is significantly less detailed about this topic. In the lines that discuss the objectives of his proposal, he only states, "we need a regular and accepted process." However, in any event, it tends toward a policy of constant exchange rates until the possibility of a serious deterioration becomes obvious.

This is the case even if it is not the case. According to what was written in the New York Times on August 20, 1943, the compromise plan does not seem to have made any substantial improvements over the originals when it comes to this aspect. Naturally, the items that a country sells abroad will not be identical to those that are represented by the standard unit. On the other hand, such units may be purchased and then transformed into the country's central bank, which has commodity reserves because of the sale of the country's own commodities in product markets. The modest amount of debt that the country owes to itself will provide the necessary funding for the project. It is possible to collect deposit profits covering commodity units of warehouse receipts in gold (or silver), and then transfer those funds to another nation to pay off a creditor in that country. If the relative purchasing power of the world's various currencies were perfectly reflected in exchange rates, it would eliminate disruptions to international trade and reduce the significance of fluctuations in exchange rates to almost nothing, at least in terms of their effects on current accounts. The only cost that will be incurred by the nations that agree to buy and sell the combination of goods is the cost of storage, just as there are no other direct costs associated with purchasing gold. In either scenario, brand new monetary resources will be made available. Again, some assistance from silver would be welcome wherever it was deemed appropriate. Gold would be used to manage all short-term imbalances in international accounts.

Deep-seated imbalances can be avoided not only by the shared monetary policy that is required to keep metal or commodity reserves in the various countries, but also by the automatic and

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appropriate movement of the exchange values of other currencies. This is because the common monetary policy is necessary to maintain metal or commodity reserves in the various countries. This is the system that will best serve the interests of nations that have enormous gold reserves, such as the United States, as well as nations that have a significant share in its production, such as the British Empire and Russia. This is the system that will best serve the interests of nations with enormous gold reserves. In addition to this, the value of the historically vulnerable gold will be preserved (or silver). Even though there is not enough space here to go into detail about commodity reserves, the scheme has a tremendous amount of potential both domestically and internationally. If this is implemented, there will be a significant decrease in the amount of volatility in company activity, employment levels, and price levels. At this point, it may be sufficient to say that in situations where a fixed relationship is in question, it will be possible to restore and maintain fixed exchange rates in most of the world, with automatic and appropriate exchange rate adjustments, only by implementing such a policy. This is the only course of action that will allow for such a restoration and maintenance. The inability of certain countries to establish a relationship with the proposed standard, either directly or via the use of gold, has been a barrier to its progress (or silver). The only choice available is an anarchy that is less peaceful than usual. Recommendations From the System on a Regular Basis It is not an exaggeration to say that these schemes, to the extent that they will offer stability, offer ordered systems, and to the extent that they may offer freedom, offer no systems, despite what the authors of these schemes may try to hide or deny. If they offer stability, they offer ordered systems. If they offer freedom, they offer no systems. The goal of one strategy is to benefit other nations by shifting some or all the cost of unemployment that would otherwise fall on the nation that is implementing the strategy, and the goal of the other policy is to benefit other nations by changing the trade agreements they have in place with those nations. Over the course of the past 20 years, the world has gained a significant amount of experience dealing with skewed exchange rates; however, it does not appear that a definitive conclusion has yet been reached. It happened that during the period between the world wars, some countries either consciously or accidentally adopted one policy at one moment and another policy at another point in time. It would be sufficient to use

Germany as an example. In the early 1920s, the market worth of the brand was never even close to what would have been required for it to correspond even with its low intrinsic value. Because

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of this, unemployment rates in the country were very low; nonetheless, the nation became a significant negotiating chip for the rest of the globe. As a result, the nation lost most of its mobile product's exports and was finally forced to take action to halt exporters. Germany learnt its lesson so well that in the 1930s it developed a policy of maintaining an extremely high exchange rate for its currency. This had the effect of improving Germany's terms of trade, which refers to the prices of its exports relative to its imports. Specifically, this had the tendency to reduce exports while simultaneously increasing imports (anywhere that the Germans could get it one way or another). During the previous time, many countries raised concerns about the detrimental effects of unfair competition brought on by imports from Germany on their respective manufacturers. However, during the subsequent time, these same countries raised concerns about the price fluctuations that their exporters to Germany were subjected to.

However, in the latter scenario, the question arises as to why the Germans are not harmed by the competition of countries with a low exchange value against the German currency, as they had previously suffered from the low exchange value of the German currency. In the former scenario, the Germans were harmed because the value of the German currency was low. The explanation is that Germany's imports are only partially subject to stringent controls, while the country's exports are subsidized. The Germans, on the other hand, had managed to address the unemployment issue (although in an appalling manner), and therefore, they looked at inexpensive imports as an essential advantage. The mercantilist fear of currency dumping is closely related to a fear of property and a Midas-like passion for money. In a properly organized national economy in which unemployment has been eradicated, the partial exclusion of imports and the partial gifting of goods to foreigners, which is the result of maintaining a low exchange value of a currency, will be part of the national economy.

This will be the case because the national economy will be properly organized. Buyers will be pleased with low-priced imports, and there can be no credible external criticism to the practice of currency depreciation from any nation that is foolish enough to ignore it. On the other hand, we would be fooling ourselves if we assumed that any voluntary international monetary adjustment could survive pressure to decrease the exchange value of the currency of a defenseless country, unless we got rid of unemployment first. In addition, if everyone had a job, it would be very difficult for any one nation to take advantage of another by elevating the value

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of its currency to a level that is greater than the buying power equivalent of that currency. In such a scenario, no one will feel any significant pressure to sell to such a nation, and the soaring prices of the prospective exports of that country would cause customers to go elsewhere for their needs. As a result, he would experience failure in every deal. In addition, economic sanctions can be imposed on any isolated renegade country if necessary. This is the case regardless of whether the country seeks to maintain the exchange rate above or below the level of equilibrium. It was unemployment everywhere that gave birth to much of the fear about "currency wars," as well as unemployment on its own turf, which, in its drive to export at all costs, had given its satellite nations to the kind pity of Germany. The control of foreign trade, which is or necessary for a country with eccentric exchange rates, can make the distortion of international trade relations even worse. Of course, exchange rates that are eccentric will always distort international trade relations.

However, eccentric rates will only injure the nations who initiate them, or in the category of illnesses that affect other countries, if an efficient strategy for reaching full employment is accomplished, it will be more of an annoyance than a life-threatening annoyance. In any event, the only way to achieve coherence in the movement of price levels is for all nations to either spontaneously adopt monetary policies that are in harmony with one another or for all nations to sign up for an international convention that includes a commitment by each nation to adhere to such policies. The spontaneous selection of the same monetary policy by most of the world's nations was made possible by the international gold standard; however, the inability of that standard to establish anything even remotely resembling the stability of price levels led to its covert abandonment in the first place. Monetary Policies That Get Along Well Together It is very doubtful that there will ever be a sustained restoration to the gold standard in its original form. The so-called managed gold standards are arbitrary and entail the compulsion of all those who adhere to gold by the nation that can make their control successful. The system of floating exchange rates is the only way to achieve any degree of international order within a framework of freedom until we ensure the general and voluntary adoption of coherent monetary policies. This is the case because the system of floating exchange rates is the only way to achieve any degree of international order. It is possible to eliminate dysfunctional fluctuations in exchange rates by utilizing currency equalization funds; however, it is counterproductive to attempt to establish even a temporary fixation in exchange rates between the currencies of countries that

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pursue different monetary policies because doing so contributes to the accumulation of imbalances in international markets rather than their elimination. The primary flaw of both the Keynes Plan and the White Plan, as well as the compromise that was reached between the two, is that the authors of those plans preferred the fixation of exchange rates, ignoring local monetary policies, and being aware of the devastating effects that could be expected in this case.

5. The Compromise That Was Reached Between the Two Plans

The compromise that was reached between the two plans also contains this flaw. The establishment of commodity reserves, in conjunction with the resumption of unrestricted buying and selling of gold (and silver) at a predetermined price, would both contribute to the stabilization of price levels and the commodity value of gold (and silver) in the nation. As a result, it will serve as the foundation for exchange rates that are fixed between currencies. It will also encourage the automatic adjustment of all other rates to the current internal purchasing power of the respective currencies, ensuring a continuous relationship between the external and internal values of all currencies and establishing an automatic order in international business and financial transactions. In addition, it will encourage the automatic adjustment of all other rates to the current internal purchasing power of the respective currencies. (a) The stability of currency rates in conjunction with unity amid otherwise unpredictable changes of price levels. The most effective instrument for achieving this goal is (b) national independence in money management (whether this includes the stability of price levels in any given country) in conjunction with the functional movements of exchange rates. An extension of the policies of the British Exchange Equalization Account, which, in its heyday, sought to drain unemployment onto its neighbors by lowering the value of in terms of currency exchange. It does not fall below the level guaranteed by the local purchasing power, nor does it tilt the freely competitive terms of trade in favor of Britain by an excessive increase in the exchange value of the British currency. Rather, it maintains a level that is somewhere in between the two. (c) A laissez-faire approach to both domestic monetary policy and international exchange rates. This is more of a permissiveness than a freedom that is restricted, and if it does pass, it will only be applicable by default. (d) The obligatory stabilization of both price levels and exchange rates

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through the imposition of necessary monetary policy on all countries, with some central banks for central banks serving as the ultimate governing authority for central banks. There would be a ferocious battle for control of such a bank, and the only way to end it would be to give the lion's part to the lion, or in the very improbable event that the eagle would win, to give the lion the lion's share. In this regard, the data that was examined by Kuttner [2018] is comforting regarding the United States of America. Heider et al. [2019] discovered that in the case of the euro area, when the policy rate is negative, banks that depend significantly on deposit financing take on greater risk than banks that rely on alternative sources of funding. This was the conclusion reached by the researchers. On the other hand, they discovered that businesses that took out loans from these banks looked to be financially limited and were not like "zombie" businesses in any way. Demiralp et al. [2019] also shows that banks in the euro area, which have an overall heavier negative interest rate burden associated with their excess liquidity and raising funds from the public, are reallocating them to higher yielding assets. These findings are based on 196 banks operating in the euro area, which represent 70 percent of the total loans in the euro area (i.e., loans). Does the profitability of banks and their ability to lend money change in a way that could lead to asymmetric pass-through because of extremely low interest rates? As policy rates approach the zero-lower bound (ZLB) and banks' maneuverability to cut deposit rates declines, there has been some cause for concern that there may be an "economic lower limit" (Coeuré [2016]). This will correspond to the rate at which the harmful effects on the banking sector outweigh the benefits, and further rate cuts will correspond to the risks that will reverse the expansionary monetary policy stance. Currently, the U.S. Federal Reserve is cutting interest rates to stimulate the economy. The "return rate" (Brunnermeier and Koby [2018]) would have been reached when this risk was realized. In addition, because banks naturally engage in maturity transformation—that is, they borrow on short terms and lend on longer terms—the flattening of the yield curve that results from maintaining policy rates at "low for a long time" and implementing UMP measures is detrimental to banks' profitability and, in the end, compels them to reduce the amount of loans they make. However, the data is inconsistent and thus far, both banks' profitability and bank lending have typically remained robust, despite maintaining policy rates and/or the slope of the yield curve low for a lengthy time in nations with exceptionally low interest rates. seem to have adverse impacts. However, they do not deny the reality that maintaining low interest rates for an extended period may have

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a detrimental effect on the profitability of financial institutions. In this regard, Klein [2020] shows that the level of short-term interest rates had a favorable influence on the net interest margin of euro area banks, which climbed considerably when rates were negative. When interest rates hit exceptionally low levels, bank lending may also be affected since the availability of credit is hindered (Borio and Gambacorta [2017] using the example of 108 big international banks), thereby diminishing the efficacy of monetary policy. However, Klein [2020] discovered that the negative impact of the falling net interest margin on bank lending in the euro area has been eliminated.

6. The ELB But Negative

Is the transmission mechanism responsible for nominal interest rates that are above the ELB but negative? As policy rates hit negative territory, banks' profitability will plummet as clients are unwilling to pay deposits at negative rates for fear of disappointment and cashing out. Eggertsson et al. [2019] contend that there is a reduction in the effectiveness of monetary policy transmission whenever policy rates move into the negative territory because deposit rates are so close to zero. The authors concentrate on the experience of Sweden and conclude that after the policy rate hits -0.5 percent, there is minimal shift to lending rates. This finding is based on the authors' analysis of the Swedish experience. In addition, the authors suggest that once the deposit rate floor is achieved, the decline in the policy rate has contractionary implications (i.e., it leads to a rise in lending rates) (i.e., it leads to an increase in lending rates). The bank credit channel of monetary policy transmission provides the foundation for their findings and conclusions. This channel exists since banks are only able to partially adjust their funding structures whenever there is a shift in the monetary policy stance, which has repercussions for the banks' loan supply. The authors contend that it is no longer prudent for financial institutions to rely on deposit financing if monetary policy is loosened, and policy rates move into negative territory. This is since the maximum rate for deposits is set at zero. As a result of the restricted flexibility with which banks may modify their financing arrangements, the impact on lending rates and the expansion of credit will be contained. The regulation of deposit rates has been partially or eliminated in all developed economies since the 1980s, and banks have gained the ability to substitute deposits with other funding sources such as financial markets. Despite this,

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the significance of the bank credit channel has been called into question since the 1980s. Girotti [2019] experimentally supports this claim in the United States between 1994 and 2008 and shows that the lending channel still exists, but its size is restricted for the typical bank. In their research, Levieuge and Sahuc [2020] found that in response to a loosening of monetary policy, banks tend to adjust their lending rates more slowly and not completely, whereas in response to a tightening of monetary policy, banks quickly increased their lending rates at the same rate. They demonstrate that this downward interest rate rigidity is even stronger when policy rates are stuck at the effective lower bound, and they suggest that interest rates should be adjusted significantly further when policy rates enter negative territory. This is because entering negative territory causes policy rates to be stuck at the effective lower bound. One complication is that if policy interest rates continue to be negative for a lengthy period, competitive pressure may push financial institutions to convert negative rates into lending rates. By drawing on the experiences of Sweden, Erikson and Vestin [2019] were able to arrive at even more precise findings: They argue that the pass-through in household lending may have been a little more gradual and less complete, but that negative policy rates do not appear to significantly distort the transmission of monetary policy. Also, using data from 5,113 banks from the EU and Japan with observations for 14 different currencies between 2010 and 2016, Lopez et al. [2018] discovered that the profitability of banks has not been affected by negative nominal interest rates so far, especially in countries with floating exchange rates. This was found to be the case in countries where the currency exchange rate is allowed to fluctuate. The implementation of NIRs Moreover, the disparities between banks with high and low deposit rates were quite minor. Even though certain mortgage rates climbed significantly after the introduction of NIRs, as was the situation in Switzerland, these observations are also substantially in accordance with the observations made by the IMF in 2017 since they were promptly rectified subsequently. This was the case in Switzerland. In this context, Corbae and Levine [2018] recommend improving and strengthening bank governance and tightening leverage requirements to prevent banks from weakening, while recommending increased competition in the financial sector in an ultra-low interest rate environment to avoid adverse reactions to monetary policy decisions. Finally, it is not obvious that the ceiling for deposit rates is zero. Negative interest rates are more likely to be transmitted when competition is present. This is since banks can provide negative rates to their corporate customers when the options that these depositors have in similar assets also

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include negative rates. In fact, Altavilla et al. [2019] shows that certain non-financial enterprises are facing negative interest rates on their deposits. Since the adoption of these policies, many of the key financial variables have broadly evolved in line with standard transmission (Arteta et al. [2016]). In general, the monetary transmission channels under NUR policies are conceptually like those under traditional monetary policy, except for the cash role. Curdia [2019] takes an interesting look at what might have transpired if the Federal Reserve had implemented a policy of negative interest rates during the most recent recession. According to their results, letting the federal funds rate to go below zero may have lessened the severity of the recession and helped the economy recover to its full capacity more quickly. It is possible that this factor also contributed to a quicker climb in inflation toward the Fed's objective of 2%. When interest rates in the eurozone go into negative territory, Mouabba and Sahuc's [2019] research demonstrates that there are still some beneficial macroeconomic benefits (between June 2014 and January 2015). However, due to the design of their methodology, they are unable to evaluate the benefits of this policy after 2015; at the same time, other measures were put into place, and it is impossible to disaggregate the beneficial effects that these other policies had overall.

Large volumes of long-term government and private securities subject central banks to interest rate and credit concerns. These risks might compromise the independence of the central bank by producing losses. This begs the question: To what degree should the central bank relax? Alternately, is there a sweet spot for the balance sheet maintained by the central bank? The answer to the second question does not appear to follow a logical progression: On the liability side of the balance sheet, the two primary components are demand-based currency and long-term debt (the central bank cannot refuse to supply an equal number of banknotes in exchange for reserves). It was brought to everyone's notice how necessary it was. The argument put out by Greenwood et al. [2016] is that huge central bank balance sheets may be a. Our research has also shown that there is no major tradeoff for monetary policy on the other side of the Atlantic Ocean because of monetary policy spillovers from either the ECB or the Federal Reserve.

These swaps will provide the appearance of considerable and at the very least sustained spillovers to parameters such as inflation and actual activity. Because the European Central Bank and the Federal Reserve do not provide any evidence of transatlantic externalities with

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their respective monetary policies⁴, there is no compelling need to coordinate monetary policy. The impact of a quick monetary policy contraction in the US on inflation in the euro area is too brief to be deemed a monetary policy externality since the ECB will not react to changes in inflation that have no influence on medium-term price stability. ECB Working Paper Serial No. 2407 for the month of May 2020 at the very least in six example scenarios. The instances of open monetary policy coordination that have place during the recent worldwide fiscal crisis do not contradict our results in any way. For instance, the coordinated decrease in interest rates that took place in October 2008 in reaction to a broad shock (the global fiscal crisis) might be seen as having the main objective of increasing market influence. Such coordination in times of crisis is only a useful communication tool to reduce uncertainty in times of emergency, as opposed to the traditional coordination system in which central banks internalize cross-border externalities from monetary policy actions. This is because such coordination is only useful in times of crisis (see Coenen et al., 2017). Finally, we found that shocks to the monetary policy of the Federal Reserve had a particularly strong impact on developing countries, resulting in considerable spillovers to those economies. Our research has led us to the conclusion that the dominance of the US dollar in the international monetary system is reflected in the existence of a "hierarchy" of spillover effects in this scenario. Shocks to the Central Bank's monetary policy have a considerable influence on the financial environment and economic activity in developing nations. On the other hand, most of the effects of the ECB's monetary policy are concentrated on trade (and surprisingly commodity prices). According to the facts that we have compiled, monetary policy moves taken by the ECB and the Federal Reserve may result in policy swaps in emerging nations rather than bilateral spreads between the euro area and the United States. We do not investigate the factors that may have led to these tradeoffs, but we hypothesize that they may be connected to the growing frictions and limitations of the toolkits faced by rising economies. Coordinating Monetary Policies at the International Level This suggests that there may be advantages for large advanced and emerging economies to coordinate their monetary policies internationally, but real-world difficulties weaken this argument (Coëuré, 2016). The actions of the ECB towards the sovereign debt crisis are also discussed in detail in this section.

7. Results

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Despite a few dissenting opinions, there is consensus that UMPs are helpful. This is important because UMPs can be reused in the future and have implications for current monetary policies (UMP has a "legacy") (UMP has a "legacy"). In a more restricted sense, FG is only about interest rates. According to Campbell et al., FG may be employed in two distinct ways. As trustworthy, the Odyssean FG is more likely to succeed in each instance when FG must offer information that goes beyond other communication channels the central bank utilizes (such as the publishing of the central bank's economic projections). However, the Odyssean FG confronts various challenges. According to the findings of empirical research, central banks are not normally reliant on the monetary policy operations of the near future (Moessner et al. [2017]). Even if central banks were to make a promise, they would still be required to find a solution to the problem of temporal consistency. If the effect that was anticipated from their pledge really occurs, then they will have an incentive to back out of their commitment when it comes time to put it into action. Because special agents would be able to predict this split and render the commitment useless, they would not be able to give the ostensible advantages that FG is meant to provide.

8. References

2017. "The Rate of Return on Everything, 1879-2015." Working Paper No. 2017-25, Federal Reserve Bank of San Francisco (December).
- A. Inoue, B. Rossi the effects of conventional and unconventional monetary policy on exchange rates
- Adjemian, Stéphane, Houtan Bastani, Michel Juillard, Frédéric Karamé, Junior Maih, Ferhat Mihoubi, George Perendia, Johannes Pfeifer, Marco Ratto, and Sébastien Villemot. ("Research | University of Tübingen - uni-tuebingen.de") 2011. Dynare: Reference Manual, Version 4. Dynare
- Al Munyif M. Currency and sudden crises: Measures and relationships (Doctoral dissertation) (2016). The Claremont Graduate University, Claremont, CA, United States.
- Al Munyif M. Currency and sudden crises: Measures and relationships (Doctoral dissertation) (2016). The Claremont Graduate University, Claremont, CA, United States.
- Asian Development Bank. 2019. Asian Economic Integration Report 2019. Manila: Asian Development Bank.
- "Bank for International Settlements (2020), Annual Economic Report 2020, Chapters I and II." ("Monetary and

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- fiscal policies: In search of a corridor of stability”)
- "Bank for International Settlements (2021), Annual Economic Report 2021, Chapter I." (“Monetary and fiscal policies: In search of a corridor of stability”)
- Barkbu, B.; Rahman, J.; Valdés, R. 2012. Fostering growth in Europe now, IMF Staff Discussion Note SDN/12/07 (Washington, DC, International Monetary Fund (IMF)).
- Barroso, J.M. 2012. Towards Europe 2020: Building a foundation for future prosperity, speech delivered at The Europe 2020 Summit of the Lisbon Council, Brussels, 27 Feb.
- Bartsch, E, A Bénassy-Quéré, G Corsetti and X Debrun (2020), It is all in the mix: how monetary and fiscal policies can work or fail together, Geneva Report on the World Economy 23, ICMB and CEPR.
- Batini, N.; Callegari, G.; Melina, G. 2012. Successful austerity in the United States, Europe and Japan, IMF Working Paper WP/12/90 (Washington, DC, International Monetary Fund (IMF)).
- Berger, Wolfram, and Helmut Wagner. 2006. International Policy Coordination and Simple Monetary Policy Rules. IMF Working Paper WP/06/164. Washington, DC: International Monetary Fund.
- Bofinger P. The Covid-19 Crisis: Inflationary or Deflationary? Social Europe (2020). Available online at: <https://www.socialeurope.eu/the-covid-19-crisis-inflationary-or-deflationary> (accessed August 8, 2020).
- Bofinger P. The Covid-19 Crisis: Inflationary or Deflationary? Social Europe (2020). Available online at: <https://www.socialeurope.eu/the-covid-19-crisis-inflationary-or-deflationary> (accessed August 8, 2020).
- Borio, C (2021a), “Monetary and fiscal policies at a crossroads: New Normal or New Path?”, Panel remarks, Latvijas Banka Economic Conference 2021, virtual, 20 September.
- Borio, C (2021b), “Navigating by r^* : safe or hazardous?”, Keynote Lecture at the SUERF, Bocconi, OeNB workshop on “How to raise r^* ?”, 15 September.
- Borio, C and P Disyatat (2010), “Unconventional monetary policies: an appraisal”, The Manchester School 78(1): 53–89. "Also available as BIS Working Papers, no 292, November 2009." (“Claudio Borio - Bank for International Settlements”)
- Borio, C and P Disyatat (2014), “Low interest rates and secular stagnation: is debt a missing link?”, VoxEU.org, 25 June.
- Borio, C and P Disyatat (2021), “Monetary and fiscal policy: privileged powers, entwined responsibilities”, SUERF Policy Note 238, May.
- Bouoiyour, J., R. Selmi, AK Tiwari, and OR Olayeni. 2016. “What Drives Bitcoin Price?” Economics Bulletin 36 (2): 843–850. [Web of Science ®],

- Bouoiyour, J., R. Selmi, and ME Wohar. 2019. "Bitcoin: Competitor or Complement to Gold?" *Economics Bulletin* 39 (1): 186–191. [Web of Science ®],
- Bouri, E., O. Cepni, D. Gabauer, and R. Gupta. 2021. "Return Connectedness Across Asset Classes Around the COVID-19 Outbreak." *International Review of Financial Analysis* 73: 101646. ("CLIMATE FINANCE IN THE WAKE OF COVID-19: CONNECTEDNESS OF CLEAN ENERGY ...") [Crossref], [Web of Science ®],
- Branson, William H., and Conor N. Healy. 2005. Monetary and Exchange Rate Policy Coordination in the ASEAN+1. ("Monetary and Exchange Rate Policy Coordination in ASEAN+1") NBER Working Paper 11713. Cambridge, MA: National Bureau of Economic Research
- Calvo, Guillermo, Leonardo Leiderman, and Carmen Reinhart (1993), "Capital Inflows and the Real Exchange Rate in Latin America: The Role of External Factors," *imf Staff Papers*, Vol. 40, no. 1, p. 108-150.
- Campbell JR, Evans CL, Fisher JD, Justiniano A, Calomiris CW, Woodford M. Macroeconomic effects of federal reserve forward guidance. In: *Brookings Papers on Economic Activity*. US (2012). p. 1–80. doi: 10.1353/eca.2012.0004
- Canova, Fabio (2005), "The Transmission of us Shocks to Latin America," *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, Vol. 20, No. 2, p. 229-251, <doi: 10.1002/jae.837>.
- Cavallo EA, Izquierdo A, Leon JJ. Domestic Antidotes to Sudden Stops. IDB Publications (Working Papers) (2020). doi: 10.18235/0000825
- Cavallo EA, Izquierdo A, Leon JJ. Domestic Antidotes to Sudden Stops. IDB Publications (Working Papers) (2020). 10.18235/0000825
- Cavallo EA. International Capital Flow Reversals. Working Papers. IDB Publications (2020).
- Cavallo EA. International Capital Flow Reversals. Working Papers. IDB Publications (2020).
- Chudik, Alexander, and M. Hashem Pesaran (2007), Infinite Dimensional vars and Factor, *iepr Working Paper*, No. 07.21, November.
- Chudik, Alexander, and M. Hashem Pesaran (2011), "Infinite-dimensional vars and Factor Models," *Journal of Econometrics*, Vol. 163, No. 1, July, pp. 4-22, <doi: 10.1016/j.jeconom.2010.11.002>.
- Clark WR, Reichert U. 1998. International and domestic constraints on political business cycles in OECD economies. *int. Organ.* 52:87–120
- Collins S, Giavazzi F. 1993. Attitudes toward inflation and the viability of fixed exchange rates. In *A Retrospective on the Bretton Woods System*, ed. M Bordeaux, B Eichengreen, pp. 547–77. Chicago: Univ. Chicago Press

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- Curve Flattened? A Semi-Structural Exploration." NBER Working Paper No. 25476 (January).
- D'Amico S, King TB. What Does Anticipated Monetary Policy Do? Working Paper Series. (2015).
- Debelle G, Fischer S. 1994. How independent should the central bank be? In Goals, Guidelines, and Constraints Facing Monetary Policymakers, ed. JC Fuhrer, pp. 195–221. Boston, MA: Fed. reserve. Bank Boston
- Duso T, Gugler K, Yurtoglu B. Is the event study methodology useful for merger analysis? (“Анализ эффективности сделок слияния и поглощения”) A comparison of stock market and accounting data. *Int Rev. Law Econ.* (2010) 30:186–92. 10.1016/j.irle.2010.02.001
- Edison H, Melvin M. 1990. The determinants and implications of the choice of an exchange rate system. In *Monetary Policy for a Volatile Global Economy*, ed. W Haraf, T Willett, pp. 1–50. Washington, DC: Am. Enterp. Inst.
- Edwards S. Financial openness, sudden stops, and current account reversals, *Am Econ Rev.* (2004) 94:59–64. doi: 10.1257/0002828041302217
- Edwards S. Financial openness, sudden stops, and current account reversals, *Am Econ Rev.* (2004) 94:59–64. 10.1257/0002828041302217
- Efremidze L, Kim S, Sula O, Willett TD. The relationships among capital flow surges, reversals, and sudden stops. (“THE RELATIONSHIPS AMONG CAPITAL FLOW SURGES, REVERSALS AND SUDDEN STOPS ...”) *J Financial Econ Policy.* (2017) 9:393–413. doi: 10.1108/JFEP-03-2017-0021
- Eggertsson, G (2006), "The deflation bias and committing to being irresponsible", *Journal of Money, Credit and Banking* 38(2): 283–321, March.
- Ilzetzki, E., CM Reinhart, and KS Rogoff. 2019. “Exchange Arrangements Entering the Twenty-First Century: Which Anchor Will Hold?” (“EXCHANGE ARRANGEMENTS ENTERING THE TWENTY-FIRST CENTURY: WHICH ANCHOR ...”) *Quarterly Journal of Economics* 134 (2, May): 599–646.
- Imam PA. Shock from graying is the demographic shift weakening monetary policy effectiveness[J]. *Int J Finance Econ.* (2015) 20:138–54.
- International Monetary Fund. 2006. “How Has Globalization Affected Inflation?” In *World Economic Outlook: Globalization and Inflation* (April), chapter 3. Washington, DC: International Monetary Fund
- Jord`a, O., C. Marti, F. Nechio, and E. Tallman. 2019. “Inflation: Stress-Testing the Phillips Curve.” FRBSF Economic Letter No. 2019-05, February 11.
- Jord`a, O., C. Marti, F. Nechio, and E. Tallman. 2019. “Inflation: Stress-Testing the Phillips Curve.” FRBSF Economic Letter No. 2019-05, February 11.

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- Jord'a, O., K. Knoll, D. Kuvshinov, M. Schularick, and AM Taylor.
- Jord'a, O., K. Knoll, D. Kuvshinov, M. Schularick, and AM Taylor. 2017. "The Rate of Return on Everything, 1879-2015." Working Paper No. 2017-25, Federal Reserve Bank of San Francisco (December).
- Jord'a, O., M. Schularick, and AM Taylor. 2017. "Macroeconomic History and the New Business Cycle Facts." in NBER
- Jord'a, O., M. Schularick, and AM Taylor. 2017. "Macroeconomic History and the New Business Cycle Facts." In NBER Macroeconomics Annual 2016, Vol. 31, ed. M. Eichenbaum and J. Parker, 213–63 (chapter 3). Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Journal of International Economics, 118 (2019), pp. 419-447
- Kyriazis, NA 2019. "A Survey on Empirical Findings About Spillovers in Cryptocurrency Markets." ("A Survey on Empirical Findings about Spillovers in Cryptocurrency Markets") Journal of Risk and Financial Management 12 (4): 170. [Crossref],
- L. Goldberg, C. Tille Vehicle currency use in international trade J. Int. Econ., 76 (2) (2008), pp. 177-192, 10.1016/j.jinteco.2008.07.001
- L. Goldberg, C. Tille Vehicle currency use in international trade J. Int. Econ., 76 (2) (2008), pp. 177-192, 10.1016/j.jinteco.2008.07.001
- Lee KS, Werner RA. Reconsidering monetary policy: an empirical examination of the relationship between interest rates and nominal GDP growth in the US, UK, Germany, and Japan. *Ecol Econ.* (2018) 146:26–34. doi: 10.1016/j.ecolecon.2017.08.013
- Lee KS, Werner RA. Reconsidering monetary policy: an empirical examination of the relationship between interest rates and nominal GDP growth in the US, UK, Germany, and Japan. *Ecol Econ.* (2018) 146:26–34. 10.1016/j.ecolecon.2017.08.013
- "Leijonhufvud, A (2009), "Stabilities and instabilities in the macroeconomy", VoxEU.org, 21 November." ("Monetary and fiscal policies: In search of a corridor of stability")
- Li, X., and CA Wang. 2017. "The Technology and Economic Determinants of Cryptocurrency Exchange Rates: The Case of Bitcoin." ("The Technology and Economic Determinants of Cryptocurrency ... - SSRN") Decision Support Systems 95: 49–60. [Crossref], [Web of Science ®],
- Liu, L., C. Matthes, and K. Petrova. 2018. Monetary policy across space and time. Federal Reserve Bank of Richmond, Working Paper no. 14.
- MM Habib, F. Venditti The global financial cycle: implications for the global economy and the euro area *Econ. Bulletin Articles*, 6 (1) (2018)
- Macroeconomics Annual 2016, Vol. 31, ed. M. Eichenbaum and J. Parker, 213–63

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- (chapter 3). Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Miles D. Should monetary policy be different in a grayer world. In: *Aging, Financial Markets and Monetary Policy*. Berlin: Springer (2002). p. 243–76.
- Momani, B. 2006. “Assessing the Utility of, and Measuring Learning from, Canada's IMF Article IV Consultations,” in *Canadian Journal of Political Science*, Vol. 39, no. 2, p. 249–269.
- Notepad Blog, Banque de France, posted September 25, 2018. <https://blocnotesdeleco.banque-france.fr/en/blog-entry/international-environment-and-us-monetary-policy-textualanalysis>
- Obstfeld, M and K Rogoff (2002): “Global implications of self-oriented national monetary rules”, *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, vol 117, pp 503–36.
- Qarni, MO, and S. Gulzar. 2021. “Portfolio Diversification Benefits of Alternative Currency Investment in Bitcoin and Foreign Exchange Markets.” (“Portfolio diversification benefits of alternative currency investment ...”) *Financial Innovation* 7 (17): 1–37.
- RS Gürkaynak, AH Kara, B. Kisacikoğlu, SS Lee Monetary policy surprises and exchange rate behavior 130, *Journal of International Economics* (2021)
- Rachel, Lukasz, and Lawrence H. Summers. "On Falling Neutral Real Rates, Fiscal Policy, and the Risk of Secular Stagnation." *Brookings Papers on Economic Activity* (1:2019): forthcoming.
- Rachel, Lukasz, and Thomas D. Smith. "Are Low Real Interest Rates Here to Stay?" *International Journal of Central Banking* 13 (September 2017): 1-42.
- Razin, Assaf and Chi-Wa Yuen. "The iNew KeynesianiPhillips Curve: Closed Economy vs. Open Economy." *Economics Letters* 75 (March 2002): 1-9.
- Reinhart, C and K Rogoff (2013): “Shifting mandates: the Federal Reserve's first centennial”, *American Economic Review Papers and Proceedings*, May.
- Rey, HÈIÈne. "Dilemma not Trilemma: The Global Financial Cycle and Monetary Policy Independence." In *Global Dimensions of Unconventional Monetary Policy. A Symposium Sponsored by the Federal Reserve Bank of Kansas City*. Kansas City, MO: Federal Reserve Bank of Kansas City, 2014.
- S. Miranda-Agrippino, G. Ricco the Transmission of Monetary Policy Shocks *American Economic Journal: Macroeconomics*, 13 (3) (2021), pp. 74-107, 10.1257/mac.20180124
- S. Miranda-Agrippino, H. Rey US monetary policy and the global financial cycle *Rev. econ. Stud.*, 87 (2020), pp. 2754-2776, 10.1093/restud/rdaa019/33194440/rdaa019.pdf
- Selmi, R., AK Tiwari, and S. Hammoudeh. 2018. “Efficiency or Speculation? A

- Dynamic Analysis of the Bitcoin Market.” *Economics Bulletin* 38 (4): 2037–2046. [Web of Science ®],
- Sensoy, A. 2019. “The Inefficiency of Bitcoin Revisited: A High-Frequency Analysis with Alternative Currencies.” *Finance Research Letters* 28: 68–73. (“CRYPTOCURRENCIES IN FINANCE: REVIEW AND APPLICATIONS”) [Crossref], [Web of Science ®],
- Steinwand, M.; Stone, RW 2008. 'The International Monetary Fund: A review of the recent evidence', in *The Review of International Organizations*, Vol. 3, no. 2, p. 123–149.
- StockJH. Reopening the Coronavirus-Closed Economy, Vol. 60. Technical Report. Hutchins Center Working Paper (2020).
- Sun Y, Bao Q, Lu Z. Coronavirus (Covid-19) outbreak, investor sentiment, and medical portfolio: evidence from China, Hong Kong, Korea, Japan, and US, *Pacific Basin Finance J.* (2021) 65:101463. doi: 10.1016/j.pacfin.2020.101463
- Sun Y, Bao Q, Lu Z. Coronavirus (Covid-19) outbreak, investor sentiment, and medical portfolio: evidence from China, Hong Kong, Korea, Japan, and US, *Pacific Basin Finance J* (2021) 65:101463 10.1016/j.pacfin.2020.101463
- Sutherland, Alan. 2004. *International Monetary Policy Coordination and Financial Market Integration*. CEPR Discussion Paper 4251. London: Center for Economic Policy Research
- Talvi, Ernesto (1995), A 'Big Brother' Model of a Small Open Economy: The Impact of Argentina on Uruguay's Business Cycle, Ph.D. dissertation, University of Chicago. (“The Influence of "Big Brothers:" How Important Are Regional Factors for ...”)
- Tan, Sui-Lay. 2016. “Policy Coordination among the ASEAN-5: A Global VAR Analysis.” *Journal of Asian Economics* 44: 20–40. Amsterdam: Elsevier.
- Taylor JB. *Discretion Versus Policy Rules in Practice*. North Holland, Carnegie-Rochester; (1993). p. 195–214.
- Trade Invoicing: Synthesis and Novel Patterns.” *Journal of international Economics* 102 (September): 173–87.
- Truman, Edwin M. 2011. *Asian Regional Policy Coordination*. Peterson Institute for International Economics Working Paper WP 11-21. Washington, DC: Peterson Institute for International Economics
- Turner, P. 2018. “The Macroeconomics of Macroprudential Policies.” In *Macroprudential Policy and Practice*, Chapter 1, edited by P. Mizen, M. Rubio, and P. Turner, 19–45. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press. [Crossref],
- Urquhart, A. 2017. “Price Clustering in Bitcoin.” *Economics Letters* 159: 145–148. [Crossref], [Web of Science ®],

- Velicer, Wayne F. (1976), "Determining the Number of Components from the Matrix of Partial Correlations," *Psychometrika*, Vol. 41, Issue 3, pp. 321-327, September.
- Vidal-Tomas, D., and A. Ibañez. 2018. "Semi-strong Efficiency of Bitcoin." *Finance Research Letters* 27: 259–265. [Crossref], [Web of Science ®],
- Voelker, Juan (2004), "Shocks regionales, dependencia comercial y desempeño sectorial de la economía uruguaya," *Revista de Economía-Segunda Época*, Vol. 11, no. 1, Banco Central del Uruguay, pp. 281-334.
- Weisbrot, M.; Åslund, A. 2012. Latvia's recession and recovery: Are there lessons for the Eurozone? panel held at the Center for Economic Policy Research, Washington, DC, 11 April.
- Woodford, Michael. *Interest and Prices: Foundations of a Theory of Monetary Policy*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 2003. [129]
Woodford, Michael. "Globalization and Monetary Control." In Jordi Gall and Mark Gertler, eds., *International Dimensions of Monetary Policy*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2009.
- Working Papers 1. <https://www.dynare.org>. Paris: Center pour la Recherche Economique et ses Applications.
- Wu, JC, and FD Xia. 2016. "Measuring the Macroeconomic Impact of Monetary Policy at the Zero-Lower Bound." *Journal of Money, Credit and Banking* 48 (2-3): 253–291. [Crossref], [Web of Science ®],
- Wu, Jing Cynthia, and Fan Dora Xia (2014), *Measuring the Macroeconomic Impact of Monetary Policy at the Zero Lower Bound*, available at <https://www.frbatlanta.org/cqer/research/shadow_rate.aspx?panel=2>.
- Yellen, Janet L. "Inflation Dynamics and Monetary Policy." "The Philip Gamble Memorial Lecture, University of Massachusetts, Amherst, Amherst, Massachusetts, September 24, 2015." ("EconPapers: Inflation Dynamics and Monetary Policy: A speech at the ...")
- Yi, Kei-Mu, and Jing Zhang. "Real Interest Rates over the Long Run: Decline and Convergence since the 1980s." ("Real Interest Rates: The Mystery of Low to Non ... - Advisor Perspectives") *Economic Policy Paper* 16-10, Federal Reserve Bank of Minneapolis, September 2016.
- Yoshino N, Miyamoto H. Declined effectiveness of fiscal and monetary policies faced with aging population in Japan[J]. *Japan World Econ.* (2017) 42:32–44. doi: 10.1016/j.japwor.2017.06.002
- Zhang R. *News Shocks and the Effects of Monetary Policy* (2019). 10.2139/ssrn.3348466
- Zwick, William R., and Wayne F. Velicer (1986), "Comparison of Five Rules for Determining the Number of Components to Retain," *Psychologic Bulletin*, Vol. 99, No. 3, p. 432-442.